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**Chemical Investigation of Pod Husk of
Cassia auriculata Linn**

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CASSIA auriculata Linn. is a small perennial shrub growing wild in Rajasthan and Central India and is well known for its medicinal and economic values¹. It has been studied for its flavonoids²⁻⁴, tannins⁵, anthraquinones⁶ and certain proteolytic enzymes^{7,8}. The present paper deals with the isolation and identification of chrysophanol, emodin and rubiadin from pod husk of the plant. Though chrysophanol and emodin have been reported from several *Cassia* species, rubiadin has not so far been reported from any.

The chloroform extract of powdered pod husk, after removing petroleum ether fraction, was chromatographed over silica-gel column using benzene and chloroform in varying proportions as eluent. It yielded four compounds one of which was a white crystalline compound identified as β -sitosterol, already reported from this plant. The three other compounds had melting points 196°, 256° and 301°.

The yellow coloured compound m.p. 196°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (M^+254) gave orange-red colour with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹ and red colour with sodium dithionate in alkaline solution¹⁰. Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a 1, 8-dihydroxy anthraquinone (1625 cm^{-1} for chelated carbonyl and 1670 cm^{-1} for non-chelated carbonyl)¹¹. The compound was identified as chrysophanol (1, 8-dihydroxy-3 methyl anthraquinone) by m.m.p. and co-tlc of acetyl and methyl derivatives with authentic samples.

The second orange coloured compound m.p. 256°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ (M^+270) gave pink colour with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹ and red colour with sodium dithionate in alkaline solution¹⁰.

Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a dihydroxy anthraquinone with one free OH group at position 2, 3, 6 or 7 (3390 cm^{-1} free -OH; 1670 cm^{-1} non-chelated C=O; 1625 cm^{-1} chelated C=O)¹¹. The compound was identified as emodin (1,6,8-trihydroxy-3-methyl anthraquinone) by m.m.p., co-tlc and ir.

The third yellow coloured compound, m.p. 310° $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (M^+254) gave positive tests with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹. Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a 1, 3-dihydroxy anthraquinone (3420 cm^{-1} , free -OH; 1650 cm^{-1} non-chelated carbonyl, and 1625 cm^{-1} chelated carbonyl group)¹¹. It was identified as rubiadin by m.m.p., co-tlc and ir of its acetyl and methyl derivatives with those of an authentic specimen. Rubiadin is thus reported for the first time in *Cassia* species.

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**A Note on the Antibacterial Action of Some
2-Anilinoacetyl-5-Nitrofurans**

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It has been shown by Sherman¹ that compounds in which the nitrofur ring is directly attached to a heterocyclic ring exhibit antibacterial activity. Since then a number of nitrofuryl heterocycles have

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been prepared and found to possess high antibacterial activity. Burch and Smith² made an interesting observation that nitrofuran containing compounds, which on cyclisation yield nitrofuryl-heterocycles, also possess antibacterial activity comparable to that of the cyclised products. More recently Closier and Islip³ have reported that nitrofurylthiazolylurea derivatives possessed a broader spectrum of activity than the cyclised nitrofurylthiazolylhydantoin. Based on these findings it was thought of interest to prepare and to evaluate the antibacterial action of a new nitrofurylheterocycle 2-[2'-(5-nitro)furyl]indole(IVa) and its derivatives. But attempts to synthesise nitrofurylindole (IVa) either by nitration of 2-(2'-furyl) indole or by the Fischer indole cyclisation of 5-nitro-2-acetylfuran-phenylhydrazone did not succeed⁴. Synthesis of nitrofurylindole(IVa-h) via the Bischler method under varying experimental conditions gave either the starting material or a non-crystallisable charred product. Usual conditions of the experiment yielded the intermediate 2-anilinoacetyl-5-nitrofurans (IIIa-h). Nitrofurans (IIIa-h), besides being intermediates for the synthesis of nitrofurylindoles (IVa-h), represent a new class of nitrofuryl compounds. The present paper describes their preparation and the results of their antibacterial evaluation.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-anilinoacetyl-5-nitrofurans (IIIa-h): A solution of 2-bromoacetyl-5-nitrofuran (II; 1.25 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) was added to a solution of aniline (I; 0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr and filtered hot to remove the precipitated aniline hydrobromide. Benzene was removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure at room temperature. The residue was triturated with methanol and the 2-anilinoacetyl-5-nitrofurans (IIIa-h) obtained were recrystallised from benzene. IR spectra of these compounds showed two sharp

Fig. 1

bands due to N—H and C=O stretching frequencies in the region of 3300-3325 and 1675-1695 cm^{-1} , respectively. All compounds analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N. The melting points are given in Table 1.

Evaluation of antibacterial activity by cup plate method: Antibacterial activity of test compounds (IIIa-h) was determined against *Staphylococcus*

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 2-ANILINOACETYL-5-NITROFURANS (IIIa-h)

Compound No. III	Name of the Compound	R	m.p. °C	Minimum inhibitory concentration, $\mu\text{g/ml}$			
				Es-2068 ^(b)	S. au-2079 ^(b)	A. aer-2283 ^(b)	Pa. aer ^(a)
a	2-Anilinoacetyl-5-nitrofuran	H	141d	5	100	10	10
b	2-(p-Toluidinoacetyl)-5-nitrofuran	4-CH ₃	134	10	10	50	10
c	2-(p-Chloroanilinoacetyl)-5-nitrofuran	4-Cl	166-7	10	100	10	5
d	2-(p-Bromoanilinoacetyl)-5-nitrofuran	4-Br	175	5	50	10	50
e	2-(o-Bromoanilinoacetyl)-5-nitrofuran	2-Br	154-5d	50	10	100	100
f	2-(2'-Chloro-5'-methylanilinoacetyl)-5-nitrofuran	2-Cl	162-3d	5	50	50	50
g	2-(o-Chloroanilinoacetyl)-5-nitrofuran	2-Cl	138-9d	10	50	50	100
h	2-(o-Methoxyanilinoacetyl)-5-nitrofuran	2-OCH ₃	132-3d	10	10	50	50
	Nitrofurazone ^(b)	-	-	5	10	10	100

(a) Minimum inhibitory concentration is the lowest concentration of the compound that prevents visible growth after 24 hrs of incubation.

(b) Furacin^R for comparison, Es-2068—*Escherichia coli*. S. au-2079—*Staphylococcus aureus*. A. aer-2283—*Aerobacter aerogenes*. Ps. aer.—*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

aureus, *Escherichia coli*; *Aerobacter aerogenes* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by the cup plate method⁵. The cups were of 10 mm diameter. Test compounds were dissolved in ethylene glycol or dimethyl formamide and (0.1 ml) placed in each cup. Incubation was at 37° for 4-28 hr. Nitrofurazone, the well-known topical antibacterial agent, was used as standard compound and solvent control was kept. Results obtained are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

None of the compounds possessed activity against *S.aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. aerogenes* that was significantly better than that of nitrofurazone; some of them even possessed weaker activity. The only noteworthy activity exhibited by these nitrofurans was against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

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Synthesis of Some Aryloxypropionyl Thiosemicarbazides and Related Compounds as Possible Fungicides

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES have been reported to possess significant biological activity^{1,2}. Many triazoles have been known to possess fungicidal³ and pesticidal⁴ action. Several 2,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-thiadiazoles and oxadiazoles have been reported to exhibit antitubercular⁵, antifungal^{5,6} and bactericidal⁷ properties. Keeping these facts in view the title compounds were prepared.

The synthesis of these compounds has been outlined in Scheme 1. The structures were established on the basis of elemental analyses and ir spectra.

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Scheme 1

The analytical data of compounds, thus obtained, are given in Tables 1-2.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R'	m.p. °C	Yield %
1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides(I) R=2-Cl			
1	H	102	59
2	4-Cl	174	98
3	2-CH ₃	157	53
4	3-OH ₂	161	45
5	4-CH ₃	168	99
3-(α -Aryloxyethyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles(II) R=2-Cl			
6	H	99	96
7	4-Cl	44	98
8	2-CH ₃	147	98
9	3-OH ₂	63	98
10	4-CH ₃	69	62

All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	R'	m.p. °C	Yield %
2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(III) R=2-Cl			
11	H	145	94
12	4-Cl	124	94
13	2-CH ₃	142	89
14	3-OH ₂	155	95
15	4-CH ₃	119	56
2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles(IV) R=2-Cl			
16	H	181	48
17	4-Cl	106	83
18	2-CH ₃	145	88
19	3-CH ₃	158	76
20	4-CH ₃	116	78

All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer.

1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides(I): α -Aryloxypropionyl hydrazines⁸ (0.01 M) and arylisothiocyanates (0.015 M) were refluxed gently in ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hrs, the solution